

THREE-DIMENSIONAL DEFORMATION AND FAILURE ANALYSIS OF TEXTILE REINFORCED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A material-adaptive 3-D analysis of textile composites based on meso-volumes and deficient spline displacement approximations is proposed. This is developed for brick-type mosaics of arbitrary anisotropic meso-volumes. Sub-division of meso-volumes, application of deficient splines, and use of the minimum energy principle provides displacements, strains and stresses throughout the part. All necessary loading and internal continuity conditions can be satisfied with requisite accuracy by increasing the sub-element density. 3-D stress analysis in a woven composite plate under transverse bending is shown. A procedure for initial failure prediction is proposed and applied.

1. INTRODUCTION

Unlike traditional laminated materials, textile reinforced composites are characterized by a variation of physical properties in all three directions. Therefore textile composites have to be treated as complex three-dimensional hierarchical structures rather than as traditional, structurally quasi-homogeneous materials. However, the direct application of numerical analysis to a textile composite structural part starting at the level of a single fiber surrounded by matrix seems to be unrealistic even when utilizing the most advanced super-computing facilities. Obviously, the analysis of a multi-level structured material has to be specified for the particular engineering problem.

In many practical situations when only displacements, static buckling loads, or lowest natural frequencies are of interest, the analysis of a "fully homogenized" textile structural part may be useful. If the information about local distributions of stresses in the structural part is needed (*e.g.* in the zones of stress concentrations or high stress gradients), the internal construction of a textile reinforced material gains importance and, consequently the next hierarchical level has to be considered. In this case, the whole structural part can be represented as an assemblage of distinct anisotropic "meso-volumes" [1-3]. Thus a homogenization procedure can be applied at the level of these meso-volumes, each containing sufficiently numerous yarns to be treated as a homogeneous anisotropic body. Starting at this level, some local "macro" failure effects in the structural part can be predicted using traditional phenomenological failure criteria. In the case when "micro" failure effects are of interest, one has to start at the next hierarchical level, namely, a single yarn surrounded by matrix. The concept of a meso-volume can be applied to this analysis supposing that a homogenized yarn element (containing a many fibers) and matrix elements represent two distinct meso-volumes [1]. It is important to point out that the internal reinforcement architecture of textile composites [4-6] is considerably more complex than that of traditional laminated composites at any of the aforementioned hierarchical levels. Hence, textile composite structures need a special approach for stress and failure analyses. Neither common theories of laminated structures with their corresponding finite element approaches nor strength-of-materials methodologies are applicable.

In a “perfect” model of a composite laminate, as well as in a perfect model of a spatially reinforced material, both the conditions of continuity of displacements and transverse stresses must be satisfied through the entire structural part. In [1] this was thoroughly discussed in the context of finite element modelling of laminated composite structures. According to the concept proposed in [2, 3], there is an opportunity to develop a general displacement-assumed computational model for a textile reinforced composite structural part using its primary “material-adaptive” partition into meso-volumes, then additional, purely computational partition of meso-volumes into sub-elements. Then an approximation of the unknown displacement fields with respect to the whole discretization introduced by these two partitions in terms of deficient spline functions can be realized.

This idea is used for the analysis of a woven composite rectangular plate in this paper. In the brick model presented herein, the material-adaptive aspect of the analysis is employed to satisfy the continuity of displacements and the necessary stress components throughout the plate. The structural response predicted by modelling the plate as a mosaic structure consisting of anisotropic homogeneous bricks is analyzed. A methodology for initial failure analysis is proposed and used for predictions of initial failure mode, and location of initial failure zone.

2. MATERIAL-ADAPTIVE ANALYSIS OF INHOMOGENEOUS STRUCTURES

2.1. Spline approximations

A general methodology for the analysis of structural parts made of inhomogeneous materials can be demonstrated on the example of a brick-type mosaic parallelepiped shown in Figure 1.a. In this case the internal boundaries separate adjacent bricks (each with unique physical properties), and the boundaries are parallel to the side planes of the parallelepiped. Let us designate the set of planes containing all of these boundaries as $P_x = \{x=x_0, x=x_1, \dots, x=x_K\}$, $P_y = \{y=y_0=0, y=y_1, \dots, y_{L-1}, y=y_L=b\}$, and $P_z = \{z=z_0=0, z=z_1, \dots, z_{M-1}, z=z_M=c\}$, with x_0, x_K, y_0, y_L, z_0 and z_M being the boundaries of the plate.

Thus, the parallelepiped contains $K \times L \times M$ structurally homogeneous meso-volumes. In general, each meso-volume has distinct properties, but in certain situations, adjacent meso-volumes have identical properties. Accounting for this is one of the key features of the algorithm to be developed.

A system of basis functions suitable for approximation of displacements in the parallelepiped must satisfy the following conditions:

- (i) Basis functions dependent on each of the $x, y,$ and z coordinates are continuous with respect to the corresponding coordinate inside the whole parallelepiped. This guarantees continuity of displacements inside the structurally inhomogeneous body;
- (ii) At least one of the x -coordinate set of basis functions is characterized with discontinuous first derivative at each of the points $x=x_1, x=x_2, \dots, x_{K-1}$ where physical properties of adjacent meso-volumes are distinct. Analogously with the basis functions from the y - and z -coordinate sets. This is a necessary condition for satisfying the continuity of the corresponding transverse stresses [1];
- (iii) Within any meso-volume, all basis functions have highest possible degree of continuity.

Splines will be used as approximating functions in the subsequent solutions. Deficient splines having selected first derivative continuities are chosen for convenience. It is easy to define the level of continuity and the degree of approximation of splines, and each variation can be realized through a small set of input parameters. Construction of the approximation splines starts by generating another three sets of mutually parallel planes: $P_\xi = \{x=\xi_0=0, x=\xi_1, \dots, \xi_{\lambda-1}, x=\xi_\lambda=a\}$, $P_\eta = \{y=\eta_0=0, y=\eta_1, \dots, \eta_{\mu-1}, y=\eta_\mu=b\}$, and $P_\zeta = \{z=\zeta_0=0, z=\zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_{\nu-1}, z=\zeta_\nu=c\}$ that have purely computational meaning. Note that $P_x \subset P_\xi, P_y \subset P_\eta,$ and $P_z \subset P_\zeta$.

The displacement field is represented in the same form as a laminated plate [7, 8]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_x(x,y,z) &= \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k U_{ijk} X_i^U(x) Y_j^U(y) Z_k^U(z) \\
 u_y(x,y,z) &= \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k V_{ijk} X_i^V(x) Y_j^V(y) Z_k^V(z) \\
 u_z(x,y,z) &= \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k W_{ijk} X_i^W(x) Y_j^W(y) Z_k^W(z)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The difference appears only in the properties of the spline functions of the first and the second sets, namely $X_i^k(x)$ and $Y_j^k(y)$. Here they must have selected discontinuous first derivatives.

2.2. Basic equations

The stress-strain equations for anisotropic mosaic parallelepiped (Figure 1.a) have the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_i &= Q_{1i}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_x + Q_{1i}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_y + Q_{1i}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_z + Q_{1i}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{yz} + Q_{1i}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{xz} + Q_{1i}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{xy} \\
 \tau_{yz} &= Q_{14}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_x + Q_{24}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_y + Q_{34}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_z + Q_{44}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{yz} + Q_{45}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{xz} + Q_{46}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{xy} \\
 \tau_{xz} &= Q_{15}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_x + Q_{25}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_y + Q_{35}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_z + Q_{45}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{yz} + Q_{55}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{xz} + Q_{56}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{xy} \\
 \tau_{xy} &= Q_{16}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_x + Q_{26}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_y + Q_{36}(\mathbf{r}) \varepsilon_z + Q_{46}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{yz} + Q_{56}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{xz} + Q_{66}(\mathbf{r}) \gamma_{xy}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where $i = \{x, y, z\}$, and $Q_{lm}(\mathbf{r})$ are step-wise functions of the position vector \mathbf{r} . The linear strain-displacement equations are taken in the traditional form with $i, j = \{x, y, z\}$.

$$\varepsilon_{ii} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial i}, \quad \gamma_{ij} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial i} \tag{3}$$

The potential energy of the plate can be written as

$$P = \frac{1}{2} \int \int \int Q_{lm}(x, y, z) \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_m \, dx \, dy \, dz \tag{4}$$

with $l, m = 1, \dots, 6$; $\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_{xx}$, $\varepsilon_2 = \varepsilon_{yy}$, $\varepsilon_3 = \varepsilon_{zz}$, $\varepsilon_4 = \gamma_{yz}$, $\varepsilon_5 = \gamma_{xz}$, $\varepsilon_6 = \gamma_{xy}$.

The work of external force is expressed as follows

$$W = \int_S q(x, y) u_z(x, y, h) \, dx \, dy \tag{5}$$

where S is the loaded part of the surface $z = h$.

2.3. The solution procedure

The unknowns U_{ijk} , V_{ijk} , W_{ijk} can be calculated from the variational equation

$$\delta H = \delta(P - W) = 0 \tag{6}$$

It can be shown that the function $H = P - W$ with the P and W defined accordingly to (4) and (5) can be written, after substitution of (1) and (2), (3), in the following tensor form

$$\begin{aligned}
 H &= (A_{ijklmn} U_{ijk} U_{lmn} + B_{ijklmn} V_{ijk} V_{lmn} + C_{ijklmn} W_{ijk} W_{lmn} + D_{ijklmn} U_{ijk} V_{lmn} + \\
 &+ E_{ijklmn} U_{ijk} W_{lmn} + F_{ijklmn} V_{ijk} W_{lmn}) + (a_{ijk} U_{ijk} + b_{ijk} V_{ijk} + c_{ijk} W_{ijk})
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where A_{ijklmn} , B_{ijklmn} , C_{ijklmn} , D_{ijklmn} , E_{ijklmn} , F_{ijklmn} , a_{ijk} , b_{ijk} , and c_{ijk} are unknown constants. The first six of them depend on mechanical properties of the materials, while the other three depend on surface and volumetric loads. The summation indices in run: i and l from 1 to l_x ; j and m from 1 to l_y , k and n from 1 to l_z . Here, $l_x = \lambda + 1 + K(m_x - 1)$, $l_y = \mu + 1 + L(m_y - 1)$, and $l_z = \nu + 1 + M(m_z - 1)$.

The formulation of the solution procedure described above is not totally sufficient: it is applicable only if all of the meso-volumes have distinct properties. For example, there is the surface element $\{x=x_2, y_0 \leq y \leq y_1, z_0 \leq z \leq z_1\}$ along which two identical meso-volumes interact (Fig. 1.a). This means that the displacements here must have continuous first derivatives with respect to x -coordinate. At the same time, this surface element belongs to the border between two meso-volumes and, according to the above procedure, the x -coordinate splines deficient at $x=x_2$ would be applied automatically (see Fig. 1.b). Thus, the algorithm should be generalized in order to delete deficiencies along all surface elements separating distinct meso-volumes inside a mosaic parallelepiped. Mathematically this means that some constraints in the form of linear algebraic equations with respect to the unknown displacement coefficients U_{ijk} , V_{ijk} , and W_{ijk} are imposed on the original system of spline functions :

$$\alpha_{ijk}^p U_{ijk} + \beta_{ijk}^p V_{ijk} + \gamma_{ijk}^p W_{ijk} = \phi_{ijk}^p \quad (8)$$

where α_{ijk}^p , β_{ijk}^p , γ_{ijk}^p , and ϕ_{ijk}^p are predetermined constants, p is the number of constraints.

The procedure worked out for this purpose is illustrated graphically in Fig. 1. First the defects of the splines X_{s-1} and X_{s+1} at $x=x_2$ (Fig 1.b) are eliminated, yielding a new system of splines (Fig 1.c).

Then, the defect of the spline X_s is eliminated, and the final system (Fig 1.d) is obtained. It is easy to prove that this procedure is equivalent to the following constraint:

$$U_{s-1jk} \left(\frac{\partial X_{s-1}(x_2+0)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial X_{s-1}(x_2-0)}{\partial x} \right) + U_{sjk} \left(\frac{\partial X_s(x_2+0)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial X_s(x_2-0)}{\partial x} \right) + U_{s+1jk} \left(\frac{\partial X_{s+1}(x_2+0)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial X_{s+1}(x_2-0)}{\partial x} \right) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Here, j and k run only the numbers corresponding to the splines of the sets $Y_j(y)$ and $Z_k(z)$ which have their supports inside the intervals $[y_0, y_1]$ and $[z_0, z_1]$ accordingly.

The same form of constraints (8) can be used to specify the initial sets of approximating splines for some particular case of external boundary conditions at the edges of the parallelepiped. Formulation of various "global" and "local" edge boundary conditions in the context of the sub-layer/spline approximation method was presented in [7, 8]. Although the formulation of boundary conditions at the edges of the parallelepiped requires some additional discussion, we shall omit this, rather focusing only on some illustrative examples.

3. APPLICATION OF THE 3-D "BRICK" MODEL TO A PLAIN WEAVE PLATE

3.1. Plate discretization

A plain weave plate having length and width a , and thickness h with the material structure shown in Figure 2 (one unit cell) is considered. The partition of the unit cell is based upon the distinct orientations within the cell. The cell is divided into 25 meso-volumes, (5 in x , 5 in y , and 1 in z) non-uniformly (the in-plane sub-element divisions are indicated by gray lines). Each meso-volume has distinct material properties, although there are rotational symmetries between distinct elements. The meso-volumes were each divided into 9 sub-elements (3x3x1) non-uniformly. The elastic properties for each of the meso-volumes were calculated on the basis of the reinforcing geometry contained within, and application of a "fabric geometry model" to determine elastic constants [9].

A square plate consisting of 50 unit cells in each direction was considered subject to a sinusoidally distributed load applied on the top surface $z=h$:

$$q = q_0 \sin\left(\pi \frac{x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\pi \frac{y}{b}\right) \quad (10)$$

with a negative magnitude of q_0 . The boundary conditions correspond with simple support on all edges. The dimensions of the plate $a/b = 1.0$, and $a/h = 800$. The material properties used for the plate analysis was a homogenized representation of the woven unit cell described above. The stress and displacement distributions associated with a unit cell whose center coincides with the center of the plate were determined. These stress and displacement values were then transferred to the detailed model of the unit cell described above to examine the local effects of bending on the unit cell structure. Application of such an hierarchical analysis permits the designer to study the local failure initiation in a large part without formulating unwieldy numerical problems.

3.2. Numerical results

The stresses calculated on the surfaces of the large plate were transferred to the numerical representation of the plain weave unit cell. Boundary conditions were determined by the displacements taken from the large plate. The stress distribution on the unit cell was principally in-plane biaxial loading. Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of u_z on the mid-plane ($z=0.5$) of the structure. In this figure, the reinforcing system can be seen clearly as it bends towards the in-plane axes. As an example of the stress distribution on the plane weave, Figure 4 shows the distribution of σ_x / σ_{x0} , where σ_{x0} is the average normal stress on the surfaces.

4. INITIAL FAILURE ANALYSIS

Initial failure analysis is carried out by investigating the local stress field distribution within the unit cell from the hierarchical analysis described above. In this example, failure is based on a stress tensor polynomial criteria. The average stress state of each meso-volume within the plain weave unit cell is calculated. Similarly, based on the geometry of the meso-volume reinforcement, a stress tensor polynomial failure criteria is determined based on the micro-level reinforcement. The terms of this polynomial were developed based on a maximum strain criteria at the fiber (micro) level. Subsequently, each meso-volume is characterized by a unique failure criteria. The average stress state for each meso-volume is applied to the corresponding failure criteria.

Figure 5 illustrates the failure criteria polynomial output for each of the elements. As can be seen in this figure, the corner elements fail first. This correlates well to experimental results which show cracking at the corner regions well before failure of the component. The next step (which is the subject of a pending paper by the authors) is the introduce damage to the unit cell through property reduction and continue loading in this incremental adaptive manner until the entire part fails.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The sub-layer/spline approximation method developed in the previous works for a 3-D analysis of laminated plates has been generalized in this work for the solution of 3-D elasticity problems for a brick-type mosaic structure. The material-adaptive approximation of displacements with deficient spline-functions is used. It allows one to eliminate, or at least localize, the unwanted jumps of transverse stresses at the interfaces. The development of internal continuity conditions depend on the physical description of the structural part, and is specifically constructed for inhomogeneous structural materials (laminates, 3-D woven, triaxially braided, and 2-D woven composites).

Calculation of material properties of each meso-volume are based upon the geometry of the actual material. Incorporating the geometric description of the reinforcement into the structural analysis yields a precise and complete theoretical description of the material without depending upon data from other sources, which may not be available. The example of a plain weave composite rectangular simply supported plate (represented as the assemblage of 25 anisotropic meso-volumes) demonstrates applicability of the method. Numerical results illustrate that there are negligible jumps

at the interfaces between adjacent meso-volumes. The procedure worked out for initial failure analysis allows one to predict initial failure mode, location of initial failure zone, and the initial failure load value. This prediction of initial failure zone is in accordance with experimental results.

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Figure 1. Brick-type Mosaic Parallelepiped (a) and illustration of procedure used to remove spline defects at the surface $\{x=x_2\}$ (b, c, d).

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the plain weave plate with meso-volumes, and sub-element mesh

Figure 3. Distribution of u_z on the mid-plane of the plain weave unit cell

Figure 4. Distribution of σ_x/σ_{x0} on the mid-plane of the plain weave unit cell

Figure 5. Tensor Polynomial Failure Criteria Values for Plain Weave Meso-Volumes